

Who

Mobilising Data, Experts and Policies in Scientific Collections

WWW.MOBILISE-ACTION.EU

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&

the TDWG Task Group:
People in Biodiversity data

is

Who

IN

NATURAL HISTORY COLLECTIONS

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Biodiversity Information Standards

**TDWG**

[WWW.TDWG.ORG](http://WWW.TDWG.ORG)



[WWW.BIONOMIA.NET](http://WWW.BIONOMIA.NET)



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# The status quo of people disambiguation in natural history collections

For centuries natural history collections have exchanged specimens leading to a distributed record of individual collectors. These individual collections have allocated a lot of time and resources to adding biographical data on collectors.

As collection-holding institutes do not tend to share their biographical database publicly, this results in a massive duplication of effort between collections.

Luckily, there are initiatives like **ORCID**, **Wikidata** and **Bionomia** that collate and make these valuable biographical data available for incorporation into natural history collection databases.

i.e. "the processes by which we resolve any uncertainty in the use of a person's name using any and all corroborating information"  
-Groom et al. 2022



## Why should we care?

Knowing who these people are and being able to identify people uniquely is essential to:

- conform to the **FAIR Data Principles**,
- to improve the **quality** of specimen data and scientific results
- **connect datatypes** such as specimens, publications, DNA sequences and other research outputs.

Register for your ORCID now  
 <https://orcid.org>



## RECOMMENDATIONS

### For Curators

- Include the ORCID and/or Wikidata ID in the collector record when databasing specimens.
- Request ORCIDs from people submitting specimens.



### For Researchers



- Sign up for an ORCID, make it public, and add at least one piece of disambiguating information (e.g. your employer, a publication).
- Associate your ORCID with all your works.

### For Database Managers



- Publish the people identifiers with the collection data to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) or to GeoCASE.

### For Publishers



- Include the people identifiers with the collection data mentioned within the publication.
- Include guidance on the use of people identifiers in the author guidelines.

## What about GDPR?

The **General Data Protection Regulation**



does not apply to dead people.

Institutions **can** store personal data of living collectors such as name, ID, date of birth/death indefinitely for research purposes without asking for consent but have an obligation to inform them.